

Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket (BANTER): Project Overview

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Abstract

The Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket (BANTER) is a project funded by the European Innovation Council. In recent years, bimodal nuclear propulsion systems have been proposed in the literature. The bimodality refers to the fact that two propulsion systems (the thermonuclear and the nuclear electric one) share an element, namely the nuclear reactor. However, in general the two propulsion systems do not share the same propellant (typically, hydrogen and xenon, respectively). Other types of propulsion systems, using the same propellant for both chemical and electric propulsion, have been proposed in the literature. Thanks to their versatility, they have demonstrated to provide lower masses and dimensions and guarantee a broadening of the spectrum of achievable missions compared to systems using only one of the two propulsive solutions. In this context, the great innovation introduced by BANTER is the first bimodal nuclear propulsion system in which the same propellant is used for both nuclear thermal (NTP) and electric propulsion. The selected propellant is ammonia (NH₃). Ammonia simplifies system design compared to cryogenic propellants but comes with the drawback of more than halving its specific impulse in NTP applications compared to hydrogen due to the higher molecular weight. The radically new technologies proposed in BANTER will contribute to bridge this performance gap. In the BANTER project, NH₃ has a triple function: i) propellant for the nuclear thermal engine; ii) propellant for the electric engine; iii) working fluid for an open and asynchronous Brayton cycle generating the required electrical power. The BANTER project revolves around two main innovations: the achievement of NH₃ decomposition into nitrogen and hydrogen within the reactor core before being accelerated in the nozzle and the use of a new electric power generation system. The first will increase the NTP specific impulse to approximately 500 s, thus exceeding the performance provided by chemical thrusters using cryogenic propellants, while the second, by exploiting the In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) of ammonia will eliminate the bulky radiators generally present in nuclear electric propulsion systems. Both innovations allow for a significant reduction in the system's envelope and an increase in performance.

Keywords: nuclear thermal propulsion, nuclear electric propulsion, bimodal system, ammonia

Acronyms/Abbreviations

AF = Applied-Field

BANTER = Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket

CVR = Research Centre Řež

IRS = University of Stuttgart

ISRU = In-Situ Resource Utilization

MPDT = Magnetoplasmadynamic Thruster

NEP = Nuclear Electric Propulsion

NTP = Nuclear Thermal Propulsion

SF = Self-Field

TRL = Technology Readiness Level

UNUPI = University of Pisa

1. Introduction

Since the 1950s, nuclear reactors have been proposed for space use in both thermonuclear and nuclear electric propulsion systems [1]. In the former, the propellant, heated by the reactor core, increases its internal energy which is then transformed into kinetic energy by the propellant expansion in a convergent-divergent nozzle to generate the thrust to propel the spacecraft. In the latter, the thermal power generated by the nuclear reactor heats a working fluid of a thermodynamic cycle to generate the electrical power for the electric thrusters. In more recent years, bimodal nuclear propulsion systems have also been proposed. In this case, bimodality refers to the fact that two propulsion systems (the thermonuclear and the electric one) share an element, namely the nuclear reactor. However, the two propulsion systems do not share the same propellant (generally, hydrogen and xenon, respectively). A great advantage of nuclear bimodal systems is the possibility to generate electrical power anywhere in the solar system, not depending on the distance from the Sun like traditional solar electric propulsion. Moreover, the inclusion of a Brayton cycle that uses the reactor as a hot source is the best solution in terms of cycle efficiency/mass ratio. Other types of propulsion systems, in which the same propellant is used for both chemical propulsion and electric propulsion, have been proposed in the literature [2] and have demonstrated to provide lower masses and dimensions than systems using only one of the two propulsion solutions, as well as guaranteeing a broadening of the type of performable manoeuvres and missions.

In this context, the University of Pisa (UNUPI) is leading a consortium formed by Novaspace, the University of Stuttgart (IRS) and the Research Centre Řeř (CVR) to develop a bimodal nuclear thermal and electric propulsion system for space applications within the framework of a 4-years project funded by the European Innovation Council: the BANTER project.

2. The BANTER Concept

The BANTER project proposes the first bimodal nuclear propulsion system in which the same propellant is used for both thermonuclear and electric propulsion. The selected propellant is ammonia. Hydrogen has long been favoured as the primary propellant for nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) systems, dating back to the 60's Rover/NERVA program [3]; its low molecular weight provides exceptional specific impulse (I_{sp}) outclassing traditional chemical propulsion systems. However, hydrogen's low density, cryogenic storage requirements, and its limited availability on potential space mission destinations complicate its use. Moreover, the use of hydrogen in interplanetary or multiple-round trip missions increases the propulsion system development cost and time due to the excessive complexity required by the propellant management subsystem. NH_3 , with its high hydrogen content and potential for non-cryogenic storage, offers a viable alternative, especially with the discovery of NH_3 resources on the Moon [4]. NH_3 simplifies the system design but comes with the drawback of reduced specific impulse, halving its performance compared to hydrogen due to the higher molecular weight. The radically new proposed technology will contribute to bridge this performance gap.

A system like the one proposed by BANTER, shown in the schematic of Fig. 1, quickly insertable into orbit and ready for use, having the possibility of carrying out multiple trips between LEO and the Lunar orbit thanks to the ISRU of NH_3 on the Moon [4,5], will be game-changing for the next decade. BANTER will accelerate the processes of building human outposts on the Moon thanks to the fast transport of the necessary cargo and the capability to act as a cargo ship also for the Lunar Gateway, providing indispensable support for a wide range of missions involving this space station. The technology envisioned by the project also makes it easier to carry out technological demonstrations of nuclear propulsion systems in orbit. In fact, one of the main impediments to the first orbital tests of nuclear propulsion systems is linked to the development of the complex propellant management system for hydrogen and the difficulties connected with the in-orbit assembly of the engine and tanks, which are still some of the main challenges of projects involving such technologies. The proposed NH_3 propulsion system allows for overcoming these difficulties thanks to the passive storage of the NH_3 , the compactness provided by the greater density of the propellant, the implementation of the bimodal system, and the dramatic reduction in overall dimensions. The system mass will also undergo a sensible reduction thanks to the expected ISRU and the increase in performance given by the decomposition of NH_3 and a newly designed nuclear reactor.

However, BANTER's great versatility is not limited to missions to the Moon. Nuclear electric propulsion (NEP) has already been demonstrated, in several studies [6–8], to be a suitable technology for missions to Mars. Thanks to its

bimodality, BANTER can not only carry out missions to Mars in full NEP mode but also in hybrid NTP/NEP mode, thus reducing transit times while maintaining low propellant consumption. Obviously, the possibilities do not stop at Mars but also extend to the outer planets of the solar system, thanks to the generation of electrical power provided by the nuclear reactor independent of the distance from the Sun.

Fig. 1: BANTER Schematic

In the BANTER project, NH_3 has a triple function (Fig. 2):

- i) propellant for the thermonuclear component;
- ii) propellant for the electric component;
- iii) working fluid for an open and asynchronous Brayton cycle generating the required electrical power.

BANTER introduces important innovations for each of the three subsystems in which NH_3 will be used. The aim of these innovations is to develop, in the long term, a compact propulsion system capable of being placed in orbit with a single launch, which can transport tons of payload to the most attractive destinations of the solar system, with a high enough operational life to carry out multiple trips, and with high performance allowing great versatility in the manoeuvres to be carried out.

Fig. 2: Representation of the main BANTER's Components and Connections

2.1 Nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) system

A fundamental principle of the innovative nuclear reactor design is to achieve the NH_3 decomposition into nitrogen and hydrogen within the reactor core before the acceleration in the nozzle. This reaction will halve the molecular weight of the exhaust gases [9] and increase the specific impulse to approximately 500 s [10], thus exceeding the performance provided by chemical thrusters using cryogenic propellants, without having to bring complex and voluminous tanks into orbit, significantly reducing the overall system dimensions and launch costs. The NTP subsystem will consist of an E-pump sending the propellant from the main tank to the nuclear reactor coolant channels housed in a single moderator block according to a hexagonal lattice. The innovative coolant channel, if proven efficient, will allow an enormous boost of the technology proposed by BANTER. A catalytic bed, composed of 0.4-0.8 mm diameter pellets, will be inserted in the inlet region to accelerate the kinetics of the NH_3 decomposition. The nuclear fuel, in the shape of coated spherical particles (diameter of approx. 0.5 mm), like those of the Pebble Bed Reactor [11–13], is in the central region through which the NH_3 flows axially. It provides the energy to increase its temperature up to 3000K. At the outlet of the channel an integrated convergent-divergent nozzle accelerates the hot exhaust gases, providing the thrust. The NH_3 decomposition will also be enhanced by the action of neutron and gamma radiation [14]. This kind of coolant channel is an absolute novelty in the field of nuclear propulsion as it has never been proposed before, as well as the combination of three effects (catalysis, radiolysis, and pyrolysis) to decompose NH_3 has never been addressed by any study.

2.2 Electric Thrusters

Different NH_3 electric thrusters will be evaluated, including the magnetoplasmadynamic thruster (MPDT) and the arcjet. MPDT (Fig. 5) is the ideal choice for nuclear electric propulsion, due to its scalability to the very high power (> 500 kW) potentially available from the reactor. Two configurations are possible for the MPDT. Self-field MPDTs exploit self-induced magnetic fields and high current densities to accelerate the propellant plasma through the generated Lorentz forces. Steady-state SF-MPDTs operation is relatively simple, and the resulting thrust density is extremely high. Applied field (AF-)MPDTs utilize an additional axially aligned magnetic field which introduces new acceleration mechanisms: Hall and swirl acceleration. The generated thrust is proportional to the applied magnetic field strength. Arcjets (Fig. 4) share some similarities with steady-state SF-MPDTs, both being composed of concentric anodes and cathodes, and both operating with an arc between these electrodes. The major difference is the acceleration mechanism. Whereas steady-state SF-MPDTs aim to fully ionize the propellant and make use of the Lorentz force of the self-induced magnetic field, arcjets simply heat the propellant by means of resistive heating from

the arc. The geometry of arcjets is also significantly different, incorporating a convergent-divergent nozzle. All these aforementioned thrusters have been proved to operate with gaseous NH_3 . However, one main limit of the operation with NH_3 is related to the strong erosion of the electrodes, posing a major challenge for an application on long-duration missions. In particular, the cathode (which typically works at an operative temperature of 1700°C and more, depending on the material work function) has shown to be significantly affected by operation with NH_3 .

Fig. 3: The 100 kW class AF-MPD thruster SX3, developed at IRS, in operation with argon propellant [15].

Fig. 4: The arcjet thruster TALOS, developed at IRS, in operation with ammonia propellant [16].

The BANTER project will mitigate the cathode erosion by implementing different strategies and modern technologies to increase the thrusters' life. One example for this is a hollow cathode design using ceramic compounds with low work functions as emitter material, exemplarily shown in Fig. 5. Such technologies can drastically improve the thruster applicability within NEP systems. In addition, the use of a cluster of different thrusters is an innovative approach to deliver different mission profiles and I_{sp} /thrust for dedicated manoeuvres [17]. Finally, BANTER will assess the possibility to improve the efficiency by performing a catalytic cracking of NH_3 in order to reduce the energy losses required for the plasma decomposition, particularly important for arcjets.

Fig. 5: Hollow Cathode Rendering

2.3 Electric power generation system

The majority of the systems proposed in the literature [18] present some significant disadvantages [19]:

- the working fluid used in the thermodynamic cycle is different from the propellant, this forces an additional fluid to be brought into orbit;

- the fluid absorbs heat passing through the walls of the nozzle and the moderator eliminating the heat generated after firing the NTP, this greatly limits the generated amount of electrical power and the times in which it can be provided;
- the only way the system has to disperse waste heat is through radiation towards open space, then the necessity to include radiators with enormous masses and envelopes.

BANTER tries to eliminate these drawbacks by using NH_3 extracted from the main propellant tank through an E-pump, as working fluid for an open asynchronous Brayton cycle. In this cycle (Fig.1 and Fig. 6, loop A-B-C-D), the NH_3 passes through the nuclear reactor to change its phase and absorb heat (increasing its temperature up to the turbine material limit). Then, the gaseous NH_3 expands in a turbine, converting work into electric power thanks to a generator connected to the turbine shaft; this power feeds the electric thrusters and the E-pumps. The NH_3 exiting from the turbine flows towards a second NH_3 tank initially empty. Different solutions are implemented to keep the pressure inside this tank below the threshold imposed by the turbine operating conditions. The tank is connected to a series of warm gas thrusters (i.e. the arcjet thrusters of the NEP system used without the electric power input) that vent the excess of vapor NH_3 by generating small thrust for the spacecraft attitude control; a flow of liquid NH_3 can be directed using an E-pump from the main tank to a mixer at the entrance of the second tank where it reduces the vapor NH_3 temperature and enhance its condensation; another E-pump connected to the second tank can extract the condensed liquid NH_3 to send it inside the Brayton cycle; the excess of vapor NH_3 can be sent towards the main tank to perform autogenous pressurization of the propellant NH_3 and maintain a constant feeding pressure for the E-pumps (reduction of cavitation phenomena probability).

The propulsion technology that BANTER aspires to, based on the previous points, will allow a dramatic boost to the performance of NH_3 nuclear propulsion systems by making it a low-cost, low-complexity, reduced mass and envelope solution, with a long operational life and huge versatility, on which Europe can rely for becoming a protagonist of the next space missions.

Fig. 6: Ammonia Thermodynamic Cycle Example in the BANTER System

3. BANTER's Core: The Nuclear Reactor

The key component of the system proposed within BANTER is the nuclear reactor, which represents the element shared by all subsystems and must comply with often opposing requirements that make its design highly complex. At the current stage of the project, the preliminarily selected reactor configuration is shown in Fig. 7. The reactor features a single beryllium moderator block containing four rings of thrust channels loaded with the nuclear fuel and arranged in a hexagonal lattice, for a total of 37 channels. Each channel is circular with walls insulated using SiC and ZrC layers. Nuclear fuel in the form of layered coated particles (such as TRISO or BISO [20]) hundreds of micrometers in size fills the internal volume of the channel so that the formed particle bed is axially traversed by the propellant flow. As explained in [21], this configuration, although generating a higher pressure drop than classic particle bed reactor configurations [22], guarantees a longer residence time of the ammonia flow in the channel, necessary to

achieve complete propellant decomposition [10]. Fig. 8 shows the thrust channels in detail: in the propellant inlet portion, a bed of catalytic particles is mixed with the fuel particles to accelerate the decomposition of the ammonia. The central part is composed only of a bed of fuel particles to increase the temperature of the gas mixture up to 3000 K; finally, the channel outlet has an integrated convergent-divergent nozzle geometry to accelerate the flow of hot gases [23]. The final portion, with an integrated nozzle, allows for obtaining the same thrust as a single-nozzle configuration while significantly reducing the axial size of the system, a fundamental characteristic for BANTER since the compactness of the configuration is one of the main design driving factors. The beryllium moderator is cooled through small cylindrical channels formed around the thrust channels; these channels absorb the heat deposited in the moderator and use it to perform the work necessary to generate electrical power within a thermodynamic cycle. The reactor core is surrounded by the beryllium reflector, which houses 16 B4C control drums for regulating the reactor's criticality. A beryllium top reflector and a graphite bottom reflector housing the channel's integrated nozzles complete the axial configuration. The nuclear reactor must be able to sustain the generation of electrical power for the entire duration of the mission, allowing at the same time the use of the NTP to carry out high-thrust manoeuvres. Since the coolant channels for electric power production are part of a closed loop, while those for the NTP thrust are part of an open one, the concept of pressure tubes, like in the CANDU reactor, will be adopted for the former to avoid the design of a complex reactor pressure vessel. Starting from this layout, a dedicated work package will provide a much more detailed design, together with multi-phase analysis, to demonstrate the reactor's capability of meeting all the required specifications.

Fig. 7: BANTER Reactor's Initial Layout

Fig. 8: BANTER Reactor's Coolant Channel

4. BANTER Test Campaigns

As depicted above, the main idea of BANTER is to design a bimodal propulsion system using NH_3 as the propellant for electric and thermonuclear thrusters, whose performance is maximized by the NH_3 decomposition process enhanced inside the innovative reactor's thrust channels. The project objectives to demonstrate the proof-of-principle of this game-changing technology involve the development and testing of 3 laboratory-scale propulsion systems: two thrust channel prototypes to demonstrate the NH_3 decomposition and verify the increase in performance, and a NH_3 -fed EP thruster to evaluate the performance in the low-thrust range of the proposed bimodal propulsion system. The analysis of the nuclear reactor, the shared component of both propulsion technologies, will provide the main inputs for the development of the other elements. Suitable neutron, chemical and thermo-hydraulic analyses will be necessary to satisfy the constraints of size, mass, safety, and operating lifetime as required by the selected mission scenario. Studies regarding bimodal nuclear configurations using NH_3 as propellant combined with a catalyst in the coolant channels are absent in the literature. Therefore, the project might have to face unexpected challenges. New methodologies may have to be applied, based on coupled neutronic and thermo-hydraulic

calculations, thermochemical and photochemical analyses, as well as studies on catalyst survivability in a nuclear environment.

The ammonia decomposition, which will provide the NTP with a specific impulse of around 500 s, is a known endothermic reaction. Recently, the energy industry has shown strong interest in the NH_3 decomposition process for the green hydrogen production [24]. In the literature, the decomposition is often analysed under conditions of ambient pressure, limited temperatures (max. 900°C), and high residence times of the NH_3 flow on the catalyst (minutes/hours). For hydrazine chemical propulsion systems [25], where the outgoing gas has limited thermal power, the NH_3 decomposition has to be avoided as it decreases the specific impulse: the reduction in molecular weight does not balance the reduction of temperature caused by the decomposition. However, NTP systems are not limited in thermal power and the NH_3 flowing inside the reactor thrust channels can receive all the heat required to trigger its decomposition without any counterproductive effect. To date, the NH_3 decomposition has never been tested under the pressure, temperature, mass flow, and environment conditions of the BANTER project. Due to the process's slow kinetics, the main doubt concerns the decomposition degree achieved at the channel's exit. BANTER will increase the TRL of the proposed technology by investigating the combination of catalysis, thermolysis, and radiolysis to accelerate the decomposition of a flow of NH_3 . Two thrust channel prototypes, not containing nuclear fuel, will be built during the project according to the results of the nuclear reactor design.

The first prototype, shown in Fig. 8, will feature a catalytic bed, a bed of inductively heated metal spheres (simulating the reactor fuel particles), and an integrated nozzle. This prototype will be placed in a highly instrumented test rig and will be subject to a scaled (compared to the nominal one) flow of NH_3 to satisfy the facility safety requirements. The measurement of the nozzle inlet pressure and mass flow will allow estimating the characteristic velocity. The same test will be repeated without the catalyst and the characteristic velocity obtained will be compared with the previous one. Thanks to the dependence of the characteristic velocity on the molecular weight of the expelled gas mixture, it will be possible to determine the effect of catalysis and thermolysis on the NH_3 decomposition reaction. Moreover, the results will confirm the propulsive performances achievable with the new type of channel proposed for the NTP.

The second prototype will be like the first one but without the integrated nozzle and designed to be tested under irradiation conditions at the LVR-15 research reactor of CVR (Rez, Prague). The test will be done at one of the horizontal channels where the irradiation conditions can be changed by varying the fraction between the neutron and photon components. The expected total neutron flux is approx. $4.1 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, with a photon component of the same order of magnitude. The coolant channel will be part of a closed circuit in which NH_3 will circulate at a pressure of 40 bar. The NH_3 flowing in the thrust channel, while being inductively heated to provide the heat necessary for its decomposition, will go through the catalytic bed and interact with the radiation coming from the reactor. A mass spectrometer or equivalent instrument will analyse the composition of the outgoing gas to determine the achieved degree of decomposition. The test can be repeated without the catalyst (i.e. replacing it with metal pellets) to evaluate the separate contributions of catalysis and radiolysis to the decomposition kinetics.

BANTER aims to use steady state MPDTs and arcjet thrusters propelled with NH_3 in a nuclear propulsion system, for the first time since the introduction of NEP. The project will contribute to the realization of this technology through an innovative methodology which involves the upgraded design of the thrusters to be compatible with NH_3 for long-duration missions and the test of a scaled version of the thrusters in continuous operation. The upgraded design will involve specific studies on the cathode and the anode, to improve NH_3 compatibility and limit the erosion of the electrodes (which is currently the most important life-limiting factor). The testing phase will then investigate the thruster performance with NH_3 in comparison with more typical propellants (such as argon) on a scaled low power thruster. The test campaign will also investigate the effect of using a NH_3 catalytic decomposition before the ionization stage, to address the effective increase in efficiency. From these results information will be extrapolated on the use of NH_3 on higher power thrusters such as the AF-MPDT SX3 developed at IRS [15].

5. Project Timeline and Main Outcomes

The BANTER project will increase the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the foreseen technologies from 1 to 4 in four years; this increment will be achieved by following a design, analysis, development, and testing strategy divided in two main activities. In the first activity, the BANTER project will model: (i) a new type of nuclear reactor that can be operated safely for many months, keeping the uranium enrichment below 20% and limiting its weight and size to satisfy the mission requirements; (ii) an innovative electrical power generation system that does not require any bulky radiator on board of the spacecraft, but uses the heat of exhausted NH_3 (working fluid) to power

warm gas thrusters and pressurize the main NH_3 tank. In the second activity, the project will design, test, and deliver three main components of the system: (i) a first prototype thrust channel for NH_3 thermal and catalytic decomposition, and a test bench to measure the decomposition grade and the propulsive performance; (ii) a second prototype thrust channel for NH_3 radiolytic and catalytic decomposition, and a test bench to measure the decomposition grade inside a pressurized flowing loop under irradiation conditions; (iii) in-space NH_3 electric thruster, where the MPDTs and arcjets using NH_3 and decomposed NH_3 as the propellant is validated. Finally, system engineering will integrate these technological developments and provide the overall system analysis to focus future developments on the constraints of onboard use.

As stated before, BANTER's goal is to raise the TRL of the proposed breakthrough technology to 4 over the course of the four-year project. The starting point is the identification of a reference mission that aligns with the European Space Agency's future exploration plans. Among the various scenarios that will be of interest in the coming decades, the choice fell on missions where BANTER can express its full potential: the ability to perform hybrid manoeuvres using high-thrust or high-efficiency propulsion, the possibility of multiple trips thanks to ISRU, the dependence of the entire system's operation on a single fluid, and the compactness of the configuration. All these aspects open up a wide spectrum of missions, among which the most attractive are those involving multiple trips between Earth, the Moon, and Mars. Careful study of the mission analysis has allowed us to obtain specific requirements for the multiple, intrinsically linked subsystems. Both the mission analysis and the methodology applied for defining the requirements are presented in companion papers. The design of the BANTER components will start according to the established requirements; this design will involve two main phases, as highlighted in Fig. 9. To start increasing the TRL, an initial design focusing on critical elements—specifically the nuclear reactor, catalytic bed channels, power generation system, and electric thrusters—will be developed. This design will guide the creation of appropriate test facilities and prototypes, which will then be used to verify imposed requirements through analysis and testing.

Subsequently, experimental campaign results will inform any necessary design modifications to help the system reach its target TRL. After integrating these modifications into the subsystem designs, experimental campaigns will be repeated during the final project period to verify the achieved TRL.

Fig. 9: BANTER Phases in Increasing the TRL

The project's second activity will focus on the thrusters and coolant channels modelling, developing and testing:

- **Nuclear reactor thrust channels:** the design of the channels will start together with the nuclear reactor design. Analytical models of viscous, non-adiabatic, and chemically reactive flow will provide a first estimate of the channel shape, the length of the catalyst and of the fuel sections, and the wall contour of the integrated nozzle. The models will also give a preliminary estimation of the degree of NH_3 decomposition obtained under certain operating conditions within the range set by the mission requirements. Various NH_3 catalyst materials will be evaluated (e.g. Ru, Ni, Pt, W, Mo, etc.) considering their maximum operating temperature and degree of decomposition they could provide. A trade-off will be necessary to determine the optimal length of the catalytic bed inside the channel to avoid excessive thermal damage of the pellets while maintaining a high degree of the propellant decomposition. After fixing the coolant channel configuration and the nozzle contour employing dedicated thermal-hydraulic analysis coupled with the nuclear reactor design, the realization of the thrust channel prototypes can start. Two versions of this channel will be developed according to different experimental campaigns they will go through:

- **Thermal Propulsion Tests:** the tests aim to determine the contribution given by catalysis and thermolysis to the NH_3 decomposition and to evaluate the generated propulsive performances. The thrust channel prototype will be a laboratory-scale model of the channel foreseen for the reactor core. It will present an inlet portion with a heated catalytic bed, followed by a section with metal spheres, emulating the fuel, inductively heated to simulate the power density profile that the NH_3 flow will face in the reactor particle bed, and will end with the contour of the nozzle designed in the previous phases. Pressure, temperature, and mass flow of the propellant at different positions along the channel will be monitored. Moreover, the channel will be placed on a test bench designed and developed to measure its characteristic velocity; this parameter, being inversely proportional to the molecular weight of the gases exiting the channel, will allow for determining the NH_3 degree of decomposition.
- **Irradiation Tests:** the experimental campaign aims to determine the contribution given by catalysis and radiolysis to the decomposition of NH_3 and evaluate the lifetime of the catalyst pellets in a radiation environment. The prototype will be a laboratory-scale model of the channel foreseen for the reactor core. It will present an inlet portion with the catalytic bed inductively heated to provide the thermal power necessary for the NH_3 flow decomposition, followed by a section with metal spheres (emulating the fuel). In this case, the channel final segment will not have the integrated nozzle and will be connected to a mass spectrometer or other sensors to estimate the composition of the gas and thus the achieved degree of NH_3 decomposition. Pressure, temperature, and mass flow of the propellant at different positions along the channel will be monitored. The channel will be part of an ad hoc developed loop, shown in Fig. 10, to perform the test at one of the irradiation channels of the nuclear reactor test facility of CVR. The development of this channel will be very conditioned by the available radiation source intensity and size, and by the facility safety requirements.

Fig. 10: Thrust/Coolant Channels Test Loop Schematic

- **Electric Thruster:** the development of the selected electric thrusters will proceed in parallel and in synergies between IRS and UNIP. The baseline for the thruster design is SX3, the 100 kW AF-MPDT developed at IRS in 2010-2011 and still subject to experimental campaigns for further characterization. These activities are flanked by the experience gathered by both the SF-MPDTs and the high power thermal arcjet developments since the 1990s. The SX3 thruster features a hollow cathode, a tungsten anode, and a solenoid capable to generate up to 400 mT of magnetic field. This thruster has been operated with argon at IRS premises and demonstrated up to 4 N of thrust, with a thrust-to-power ratio of 36 mN/kW. The specific impulse reached up to 4500 s with argon propellant. The baseline for the arcjet design is the at IRS developed HiPARC, a high-power arcjet with a power level of 100 kW. The design phase of BANTER will investigate material compatibility with NH_3 , with particular emphasis on the anode materials, to limit the erosion of the electrode. The cathode will be subject to a dedicated development phase to increase the compatibility with NH_3 , investigating different technologies such as refractory metals alloys and hollow cathodes with low work-function ceramic compounds, among others. A dedicated literature review will be the first step to select material compatibility. Reduced order modelling will then be employed to address the life of the components facing the NH_3 plasma. The thruster design will be focused on the development of a scaled low-power model of the AF-MPDT and the arcjet of up to 1 kW of power. The low-power version will improve the feasibility of

testing within IRS facilities with NH_3 propellant and reduce the complexity of the testing phase. These thrusters will be manufactured and tested at IRS to address the performance with NH_3 and dissociated NH_3 in comparison with a conventional propellant such as argon. The cathode technologies selected for the NH_3 will be tested in stand-alone (e.g. without the thruster) at UNIPI in a relevant environment, and in the second phase coupled with the thrusters at IRS (the test will be performed in the vacuum chamber shown in Fig. 11). The outcome of these test campaigns will be used to prepare the roadmap for the future development of the high-power thrusters, by extrapolating the behaviour to high power.

Fig. 11: IRS Test Campaign Selected Vacuum Chamber. [26]

6. Conclusions

The developed technologies will give a great impact on the European space industry thanks to the possibility of greatly reducing the system development and launch cost compared to the classical NTP systems using hydrogen as propellant. At the same time, the BANTER propulsion system will provide superior performance to any chemical one. The combination of reduced costs and high performance would allow Europe to take the market portion connected to missions for which hydrogen systems are too complex and expensive and chemical systems too poorly performing; these missions are the commercial trips to the Moon and Mars, i.e. the main targets of the next space age. The technology envisioned by the project also makes it easier to carry out technological demonstrations of nuclear propulsion systems in orbit and to bridge the European gap in developing these technologies compared to the United States. In fact, one of the main impediments to the first orbital tests of nuclear propulsion systems is linked to the development of the complex propellant management system for hydrogen and the difficulties connected with the in-orbit assembly of the engine and tanks. The proposed NH_3 propulsion system allows for overcoming these difficulties thanks to the passive storage of the NH_3 , the compactness provided by the greater density of the propellant, the implementation of the bimodal system, and the dramatic reduction in overall dimensions. The system mass will also undergo a sensible reduction thanks to the expected ISRU, the increase in performance given by the decomposition of NH_3 , and the newly designed nuclear reactor. However, many risks linked to the extremely innovative proposed technologies must be addressed; the first risk of failure is connected the design and analysis of the nuclear reactor layout. Given the limitations on mass and fuel enrichment, key aspects that should be assessed are: (i) initial reserve reactivity; (ii) reactor management and performance when operated as electric power or thrust generator; (iii) reactor operational life; (iv) satisfaction of the safety requirements of the mission scenario. The second critical issue is linked to the development of the catalyst pellets to be inserted in the inlet section of the thrust channels. Although different types of catalysts are proposed in the literature to enhance the decomposition of NH_3 , it is not easy to establish a priori which could be the most suitable catalyst to develop during the project. In the proposed propulsion system, the catalyst will have to demonstrate high efficiency and long operational life with an NH_3 flow at high pressures (40-70 bar), high flow rates (1-10 kg/s), and in an environment characterized by the presence of nuclear radiation and high temperatures (500-1500 K). Tests on catalytic NH_3 decomposition under the above conditions are not reported in literature, thus the BANTER project will be a cutting-edge study that might have an impact in many sectors, as described later. The third high-risk aspect of the objectives set by the project concerns the experimental campaigns. In theory, the combination of catalysis, thermolysis, and radiolysis should be able to trigger the NH_3 decomposition process within the coolant channels. However, there is no state-of-the-art study regarding this process, the combination of these phenomena, or the setup of related experimental activities. Even in this sense, BANTER is a pioneering project: it aims to create two new experimental campaigns characterized by

innovative setups, the results of which cannot be predicted based on other studies. Finally, the design, analysis, and testing of the MPDTs and arcjets, although already proposed in the literature, will have highly innovative components such as a novel cathode and different anode materials, and will be tested with dissociated NH_3 to investigate the increase in efficiency. One major risk in the development of NEP systems is testing the thruster in a relevant environment (e.g., with the exact power profile given by the reactor and the power generator). In BANter, the team will investigate the occurrence of non-stationary behaviours that might affect the thrusters' performance, and the suitable measurements to mitigate these risks. These aspects will influence the entire development process, potentially giving rise to difficult problems to solve. All these considerations make BANter a high-risk/high-gain research project, which, if successful, will give a significant boost to the nuclear propulsion in space applications.

Acknowledgements

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme under agreement N° 101186520. BANter, Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket.

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Funded by
the European Union

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